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Reconstruction Identity of State Defense in the Movie “Salam Bela Negara”

Firdaus Noor¹, Fitria Ayuningtyas², Siti Maryam³

¹ Communication Department, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Pembangunan Nasional Veteran Jakarta

² Communication Department, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Pembangunan Nasional Veteran Jakarta

³ Communication Department, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Pembangunan Nasional Veteran Jakarta

Corresponding Author: Fitria Ayuningtyas. Email: Fitria.Irwanto@upnvj.ac.id

Abstract

Educations world faces various challenges in the future. Due to that matter, media is real globalizations instrument to build character especially for the young generation. The young generation or mostly called as millennial generation have high tendency to follow the western culture which is not necessarily aligned with east culture, especially with Indonesia culture. Refer to that matter, Fiber Production as one of creativity forum in the field of cinematography that initialize to made a movie with theme defense the nation. This movie story about five students affected by the impact of globalization that manifested in hedonics lifestyle and away from the love of their country. Eventually, they realized when they began with program Kuliah Kerja Nyata (KKN) in an isolated area. They finally understood that they could love Indonesia with simple way. The purpose of this research refers to this movie is trying to shift the defense of the concept of the nation. The theory in this research is semiotics, defense of the nation through the movie. This research uses social constructivism approach through analysis of Semiotics who tried to interpret by way of describing a sign through the meanings of connotation and denotation or ideology that is represented in the movie Salam Bela Negara. The result of this research, defense the nation not always relate with the military, but it could be applied in daily life through positive contribution.

Keywords: Defense, Identity, Movie, Semiotics

INTRODUCTION

Educations world faces various challenges in the future. Due to that matter, media is real globalizations instrument to build character especially for the young generation. The young generation or mostly called as **millennial generation** have high tendency to follow the western culture which is not necessarily aligned with east culture, especially with Indonesia culture.

In a globalized world in which national and ethnic diversity has become more visible than ever before. The intensification of globalization processes has prompted the transformation of the classical nation-state by

breaking its monopoly over the economy, defense, the media, and culture, among many other aspects and functions. Rising global interdependence and the emergence of transnational political and economic forces are shifting the locus of real decision-making elsewhere. At the same time, small political and economic units have become functional in a globalized world, and this in part accounts for the unexpected salience which nations without states are currently acquiring.

The spirit of credential cache for the identity of state defense manifest in the creation of this movie, actually defense the nation not always relate with military or only build the infrastructure. But also empower indigenous people, through pride and appreciation on the perceived value of culture to grow a feeling of love to the country. Refer to that matter, Fiber Production as one of creativity forum in the field of cinematography that initialize to made a movie with theme defense the nation in order to apply the prompt transformation of the nation-state. This movie story about five students affected by the impact of globalization that manifested in hedonics lifestyle and away from the love of their country. Eventually, they realized when they began with program *Kuliah Kerja Nyata* (KKN) in an isolated area. They finally understood that they could love Indonesia with simple way.

The Purpose of This Research

The purpose of this research refers to this movie is trying to shift defense of the concept of the nation. The theory in this research is semiotics, defense of the nation and movie.

DEFINITION OF CONCEPT

Globalization and National Identity

At present, national identity is one of the most powerful forms of collective identity. National identity is based upon the sentiment of belonging to a specific nation, endowed with its own symbols, traditions, sacred places, ceremonies, heroes, history, culture, and territory. The emotional charge that individuals invest in their land, language, symbols, and beliefs while building up their identity, facilitates the spread of nationalism. There is a political dimension to national identity. It refers to the wish of those sharing a common national identity to have the right and the power to decide upon the political destiny of the nation they belong to.

The defining criteria of identity are continuity over time, and differentiation from others, both fundamental elements of national identity. Continuity springs from the conception of the nation as a historically rooted entity that projects into the future. Differentiation stems from the consciousness of forming a community with a distinctive shared culture attached to a concrete territory, both elements leading to the distinction between members and 'strangers,' 'the rest,' 'the outsiders.' Classical nation-states have invariably sought to homogenize their populations and still in them a sense of common national identity. Wherever the nation-state encountered resistance to its objective, it did not hesitate to apply tough measures ranging from forced assimilation to repression, discrimination, or even mass deportations of people and genocide. Its objective was the annihilation of internal cultural difference (Guibernau:2004).

Media and Education

Even more important, national education continues to play a fundamental part in defining the national community and supplying a sense of continuity and purpose to the very existence of the nation-state. National education as Gellner (1983) demonstrated, equips individuals with the language and culture which will allow them to live and work within a given society. The importance of controlling the national curricula becomes apparent when the nation-state decides on such vital issues as:

- a. The content of national history;
- b. Whether to include the languages and cultures of minority nations and ethnic groups as forming a part of the national culture;
- c. What religions, if any, should be taught to students, and;
- d. How other countries, peoples, and cultures are to be presented.

As a consequence of globalization, the state is gaining greater control over the education system and fighting to increase its control over some of the media. Simultaneously, however, globalization has made possible the creation of continuous flows of information which cut across state boundaries. There is some kind of inherent contradiction concerning the effects of globalization upon the state's capacity to impose a homogeneous image of the nation (Guibernau:2004).

Movie

The movie can describe as a story or event recorded by a camera as a set of moving images and shown in a theatre or on television; a motion picture (Stam & Miller, 2000). The term cinematography is from the Greek roots meaning "writing with motion." At the heart of it, filmmaking is shooting. It is the process of taking ideas, words, actions emotional subtext, tone and all other forms of non-verbal communication and rendering them in a visual term.

METHOD

For Sebeok, this system is grounded in the organism's body, which routinely converts the external world of experience into an internal one of representation in terms of the particular features of the modelling system with which a specific species is endowed.

Sebeok has transformed semiotics back into a 'life science,' having relocated it, in effect, to its roots in medical biology. In other words, he has uprooted semiotics from the philosophical, linguistic, and hermeneutic terrain in which it has been cultivated for centuries and replanted it in the larger biological domain whence it sprang originally (Sebeok, 2001:5-6).

Semiology is the idea of a general study of the sign systems which make up our societies. Taking its cue from Saussure's model of linguistics, semiology should ultimately encompass linguistics, since language is merely one of the systems of signs which semiology will study (Allen, 2003:40). In the element of the Barthes takes up the distinction and developed by linguist Louis Hjelmslev (Allen, 2003:50). Barthes described that a sign thought the meanings of connotation and denotation or ideology that is represented in the movie Salam Bela Negara.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

At present, national identity is one of the most powerful forms of collective identity. National identity is based upon the sentiment of belonging to a specific nation, endowed with its own symbols, traditions, sacred places, ceremonies, heroes, history, culture, and territory. Two major implications derive from this. First, a common national identity favours the creation of solidarity bonds among the members of a given community and allows them to imagine the community they belong to as separate and distinct from others. Second, individuals who enter a culture emotionally charge certain symbols, values, beliefs, and customs by internalizing them and conceiving them as part of themselves.

Educations world faces with various challenges in the future. Due to that matter, media is real globalizations instrument to build character especially for the young generation. The young generation or mostly called as millennial generation have high tendency to follow the western culture which is not necessarily aligned with east culture, especially with Indonesia culture. Refer to that matter, Fiber Production as one of creativity forum in the field of cinematography that initialize to made a movie with theme defense the nation. The movie with theme defense the nation. This movie story about five students affected by the impact of globalization that manifested in hedonics lifestyle and away from the love of their country. Eventually, they realized when they began with program Kuliah Kerja Nyata (KKN) in an isolated area. They finally understood that they could love Indonesia with simple way.

Figure 1: Scene 17

Figure 2 : Scene 23

Figure 3: Scene 25

Figure 4: Scene 26

Scene 11 shows that even though only release ceremony of KKN' activity but the atmosphere turned into anxiousness. The result of this research, defense the nation not always relate with the military, but it could be applied in daily life through positive contribution.

Scene 17 shows that a scene eager to learn about sharing to children around that place to spread about culture tolerance which was the predecessor to the establishment of Indonesia country.

A scene that does construction dialogue from the youth pledge's covenant that was born on October 28, 1928. The youth pledge 1928 was an interpretation as the clumping attitude from all the youth from numerous ethnic and cultural in Indonesia such as *Jong Java*, *Jong Selebes*, *Jong Ambon*, and *Jong Sumatera*. This scene shows that the existence of unity the ethnic and cultural in a container named as Indonesia.

Scene 23, show some actions in an effort to capture the impression that the audience enters into cultural rituals. Some bamboo musical instruments become the object of recording. Bamboo musical instruments have a "round" sound that can make listeners relaxed. The natural colour gradation of bamboo can give the impression of unification. Both the union between humans and humans, humans with nature, and other fellow living beings. Black clothes that are connoted as traditional respect for ancestors. *Pengadeganan* is done in order to capture the value of mutual cooperation ideology, gratitude, and give to each other human beings and nature.

Scene 25: show the local product about oyster mushroom cultivation with the purpose of introducing the natural beauty in the country to the public and eventually prefer the domestic product.

Scene 26: In the final scene of this movie, the generation of millennial are fascinated by the beauty of the earth,

after tracing the facts, cultural policies and the uniqueness of history about Indonesia in their KKN journey so to blow the inspiration to love the country in a simple way.

CONCLUSION

Globalization is dramatically transforming the context within which political action takes place and forces the nation-state to fundamentally recast its nature in order to react to unprecedented challenges concerning state power and world politics. Because of this globalization education's world faces with various challenges in the future. The young generation or mostly called as millennial generation have high tendency to follow the western culture which is not necessarily aligned with east culture, especially with Indonesia culture. In the century of 21, relatedness in the world to trying to create the credential cache for identity as under review with the point of futuristic view.

Recently, identity only can be found in tradition and religion, while in other sectors such as politics and economy has been biased. Refer to those problems, with togetherness in order to the change of era, therefore, Fiber Production have an idea to create a movie about the identity of state defense with the title of the movie : Salam Bela Negara. This movie tries to reconstruct about the concept of state defense which really identic and familiar with the military, actually identity of state defense with the concept "ourselves" in the society that is capable of shearing hope by using the current the change of era. No exception to the presence of the industrial revolution 4.0.

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